

Two newly developed glutinous rice varieties for Assam, India

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We developed high-yielding glutinous rice varieties Kmj 3-292 (Bhogali) and Kmj 3-296-3 (Rongili) from a cross between Ghew Bora, a traditional tall, glutinous rice, and Kmj 1-52-2, a locally developed semidwarf nonglutinous rice. Kmj 3-292 and Kmj 3-296-3 have been recommended for planting in sali (winter) season in Assam under flood-free, medium to shallow water condition.

Glutinous rices grown in Assam are generally tall, traditional, photoperiod-sensitive varieties with very low yield. Farmers accepted Kmj 3-292 and Kmj 3-296-3 because of their high yield and grain quality. (See Table 1 for important characteristics of these varieties.)

Kmj 3-292 is a semidwarf with an average height of about 100 cm. Kmj 3-296-3 is a tall (150 cm), stiff-strawed variety. Both were tested at different locations during sali season (Table 2). Average duration to 50% flowering was 129 d for Kmj 3-292 and 133 d for Kmj 3-296-3. Although mid-Jul is the best time for transplanting, these varieties can be planted until Aug (using 60-d-old seedlings) with little effect on normal yield.

Stickiness and acceptable taste are the important characters of glutinous rice in Assam. These high-yielding varieties are compatible with local glutinous rice varieties for stickiness, taste, and cooking time. ■

Table 1. Important characteristics of Kmj 3-292 and Kmj 3-296-3. Assam, India.

Character	Kmj 3-292	Kmj 3-296-3
Panicle length (cm)	24.2	27.5
Grain length (mm)	9.7	8.4
L:B of grain	4.3	3.1
Kernel length (mm)	6.8	6.1
L:B of kernel	3.50	2.62
1,000-grain wt (g)	25.0	24.8
Husk color	Pigmented	Straw
Kernel color	White	White
Endosperm type	Glutinous	Glutinous
Abdominal white	Opaque	Opaque

Table 2. Grain yield of Kmj 3-292 and Kmj 3-296-3 in various locations, Assam, India.

Location	Year	Yield (t/ha)		
		Kmj 3-292	Kmj 3-296-3	Local glutinous
RARS, Titabar	1985	4.0	3.5	2.6
RARS, Titabar	1988	5.4	3.4	2.8
RARS, Titabar	1989	3.8	3.4	2.6
<i>All India Rice Improvement Project</i>				
Chiplima	1991	4.6	6.0	-
Cuttack	1991	5.7	5.1	-
Karimganj	1991	3.0	3.6	-
Raipur	1991	2.2	2.9	-
Farms (av of 5 locations)	1989	3.3	3.6	2.5

Yield performance of rice hybrids in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated 20 IRRI rice hybrids developed from cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A at three irrigated locations in Cuu Long Delta. Uniform trials using a randomized block design with three replications were conducted in 1993 dry season. Single seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 8-m² plots. Fertilizer rate was 100-40-30 kg NPK/ha. High-yielding

variety OM90-9 was used as a check.

Yields of hybrids ranged from 1.7 to 6.6 t/ha (Table 1). Low yields of some hybrids were due to high spikelet sterility and hopperburn, caused by brown planthopper. Hybrid IR62829 A/IR47310-94-4-3-1 R was ranked first at two locations and first on average among hybrids studied. It matured in 105 d, 1 wk earlier than the check (Table 2).

Although none of the hybrids showed significant yield advantage over the check, a few promising hybrids, including IR62829 A/IR47310-94-4-3-1 R, IR58025 A/IR54742-22-19-3 R, and IR58025 A/IR32358-90-3-3 R, will be evaluated further. ■

Table 1. Yield (t/ha) of rice hybrids at 3 locations in Cuu Long Delta, 1993 DS.

Hybrid	Location			Av
	Omon	Tanhiep	Binhduc	
IR62829 A/IR47310-94-4-3-1 R	5.8	7.3	6.8	6.6
OM90-9 (check)	5.3	6.5	7.4	6.4
IR58025 A/IR54742-22-19-3 R	4.9	5.3	7.5	5.9
IR58025 A/IR32358-90-3-3 R	4.8	5.7	6.7	5.8
IR62829A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	5.7	5.0	5.8	5.5
IR62829 A/IR54742-22-19-3 R	4.5	5.0	6.5	5.4
IR58025 A/IR35366-28-3-1-3-2-2 R	4.1	5.5	6.2	5.3
IR58025 A/IR21567-18-3 R	4.7	4.5	6.4	5.2
IR58025 A/34686-179-12-1 R	3.9	4.5	6.5	5.0
IR58025 A/IR19058-107-1 R	3.8	4.9	5.4	4.7
IR58025 A/IR72 R	3.0	5.3	4.9	4.4
IR62829 A/IR32809-26-3-3 R	3.1	4.7	4.7	4.2
IR62829 A/IR44675-101-3-3-2-2 R	3.2	4.0	5.0	4.1
IR58025 A/IR32809-26-3-3 R	3.1	5.3	3.2	3.9
IR62829 A/IR40750-82-2-3 R	3.4	5.1	2.9	3.8
IR62829 A/IR28238109-1-3-2-2 R	2.8	4.9	2.7	3.5
IR58025 A/IR52256-5-2-2-1 R	2.1	3.6	3.8	3.2
IR58025 A/IR35454-18-1-2-2-2 R	1.4	3.3	4.3	3.0
IR58025 A/40750-82-2-2-3 R	1.3	3.4	3.8	2.8
IR62829 A/IR37839-101-1-1-1 R	1.5	1.8	3.5	2.3
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	0.4	1.8	2.9	1.7
LSD (0.05)	1.0	0.7	0.9	

Table 2. Agronomic characters of promising rice hybrids. CLRR, Omon, Vietnam, 1993 DS.

Hybrid	Growth duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/plant (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Spikelet sterility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)
IR62829 A/IR47310-94-4-3-1 R	105	98	15.3	74	31	26
IR58025 A/IR54742-22-19-3 R	105	101	11.9	74	36	26
IR58025 A/IR532358-90-3-3 R	109	107	10.6	91	29	26
OM90-9 (check)	112	106	12.1	68	26	25

Kamini: a quality rice released in Bihar, India

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In areas of Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, and West Bengal, high-quality scented rice varieties are cultivated for use in specialty foods. Their price is at least 2-3 times more than that of ordinary varieties.

There are many tall, photoperiod-sensitive, high-quality scented varieties grown around the region. They have short, fine grains and excellent cooking quality. Popular variety Sugandha, released in the 1980s, has become highly susceptible to blast (BI) and bacterial blight (BB). To identify high-yielding varieties to replace

Sugandha, all available land races were collected, purified, and tested in varietal trials.

One of these is Katarni, which is grown intensively in the Bhagalpur division of Bihar. SBR 80-643-14-1-1, one of the six ecotypes of Katarni, yielded more than checks and was released as Kamini.

During 5 yr of yield trials, Kamini averaged 2.9 t/ha, compared with 2.5 t/ha for check Sugandha (see table). Growers highly preferred Kamini to other varieties.

Kamini is tall, photoperiod-sensitive, and tolerant of brown spot, BI, and BB. It has excellent aroma and cooking quality, especially for *palao*, a specialty rice food. It is a late aman (Jun/Jul-Dec) season variety suitable for rainfed lowland conditions of Bihar and eastern Uttar Pradesh. ■

Performance of SBR80-643-14-1-1 in uniform variety trials, Bihar, India, 1985-89.

Year	Entry	Yield (t/ha)				
		Sabour	Tiloundha	Patna	Pusa	Av
1985	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.4	2.6	3.0	2.1	2.6
	BR9	1.3	2.4	2.0	1.5	1.9
	Sugandha	1.5	-	3.4	2.0	2.2
	LSD	450	402	706	591	
	CV (%)	15.8	11.7	25.6	16.1	
1986	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.0	-	3.3	2.6	2.6
	BR9	1.3	-	3.3	1.9	2.1
	Sugandha	1.1	-	2.8	2.5	2.1
	LSD	323	-	350	-	
	CV (%)	13.9	-	14.5	-	
1987	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.9	-	3.4	-	3.1
	BR9	-	-	-	-	-
	Sugandha	2.6	-	2.5	-	2.5
	LSD	412	-	460	-	
	CV (%)	9.4	-	12.6	-	
1988	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.8	-	4.2	-	3.5
	BR9	1.9	-	2.6	-	2.2
	Sugandha	2.6	-	4.0	-	3.3
	LSD	470	-	380	-	
	CV (%)	11.6	-	15.6	-	
1989	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.7	-	2.4	-	2.7
	BR9	1.9	-	-	-	1.9
	Sugandha	2.2	-	2.3	-	2.2
	LSD	354	-	218	-	
	CV (%)	10.2	-	12.1	-	

Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15: a high-quality variety in Hunan, China

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Semidwarf 86-70 (selected from IR19274-26-2-3-1-2) is a long-grained, high-quality, high-yielding variety with multiple pest resistances and wide adaptability. 86-70 was released as Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 in Hunan Province in March 1993.

The variety has an average growth duration of about 118 d. Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 performed well in 1990-91 regional trials in early rice areas. Average grain yield was 6.4 t/ha.

Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 has grain length of 7.5 mm, 3.8 L-W ratio, 1.8% average chalkiness score, high translucency, 69 mm gel consistency, alkali spreading value of 7, 19.6% average amylose content, and 9.3% protein content. Cooked grain is soft and tastes good.

Hunan soft rice is the trade name of Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15. This variety won the Golden Prize at the First Agricultural Product Exhibition of China in Oct 1992. Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 was grown on 30,000-40,000 ha in Hunan Province in 1992 and is spreading quickly in Hubei, Jiangxi, Zhejiang, and Fujian provinces. ■

Performance of IRRI rice hybrids at Rice Research Institute (RRI), Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Pakistan

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Twenty-one hybrids using CMS lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A were evaluated at RRI with local checks KS282 and IR6. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications conducted during 1992 kharif (monsoon) season. We transplanted 35-d-old seedlings on 15 Jul 92. Net plot size was 2 × 6.25 m² with a plant-to-plant distance of 23 cm. Fertilizer was applied at 100-50-0 kg NPK/ha. Recommended plant protection measures were adopted. We randomly selected 15